

Expense Tracker Web Application

Mallika Mittal¹, Vidhi Maheshwari², Rinkaj Solanki³, Nidhi⁴
 Student^{1,2,3}, Associate Professor⁴
 Department of Computer Science,
 Delhi Technical Campus, Greater Noida, Uttar Pradesh, India

Abstract:- Budget Tracker is an easy-to-use daily cost management system, effectively managing daily web-based programs that reduce the need for handy manuals that keep records neatly and easily access user-stored data. The web application "Expense Tracker" is designed to manage daily expenses efficiently and effectively. By using this app we can reduce hand counts for daily expenses and track expenses. In this application, the user can give his salary to calculate his total cost per day and these results will be stored for each user. The app has a system for predicting the income and expenses of a manager using data mining. In this application, there are 3 entries such as manager, manager and employees. Administrator reserves the right to add, edit, remove manager, add, edit, remove employees, and receive all custom reports. To the Administrator, the rights are to increase the type of expenditure, verify costs, increase revenue type, verify revenue and generate reports. For employees, the rights to add and arrange costs, income and statistics, and shipping to be guaranteed.

I. INTRODUCTION

Since the beginning of human civilization, humans have been able to change their destiny in order to buy or sell. Since then, it has become an integral part of our daily lives. Most of us have a steady income and receive it on time (i.e., daily, monthly, yearly, etc.). In addition, everyone follows a strict spending budget. Generally, the budget is compiled in stages. Categories vary, for example, food, entertainment, transportation, education, health, clothing, and more. However, expenditure is limited to budget revenue. For this reason, we need to track our expenses so that they do not exceed our budget. In the old days, people tracked their own expenses, which meant using a pen and paper would be very difficult and time consuming. Nowadays the advent of electronic devices such as smartphones and computers has made our lives easier and faster. We may use computers to track your daily expenses using software available online and offline. There are other applications that can track daily expenses. These applications use a manual input system from the keyboard, which is tedious and time consuming. To meet the challenge of avoiding input, we suggest the best way to do the same things in an automated and efficient way that takes less time. Under the proposed method, users can dispose of, complete and monitor data.

II. BACKGROUND STUDY

The idea of developing this project in the mobile platform for the convenience of users. Because whenever they make an immediate expense, they can add to the mobile app. Another concern is keeping personal expenses is a GREAT problem, in everyday expenses we often do not know where the money is going. Some of the most common methods used to deal with this problem in common situations are like using sticky notes by regular users. As this shows it is a different approach used by different people. This makes use of this data inconsistent. There are still problems in areas such as there is no guarantee of data interoperability, there is a chance that important inputs will be missed and manual errors may creep in. Data recorders are not always managed, and it can be a busy process to have a general idea of those costs. We believe it is a useful design and mobile application that addresses these issues. Thus that app is able to record costs and provide a comprehensive view of the easy to use user interface and this app.

III. COMPARATIVE STUDY

Tracking daily expenses is nothing new. Many traditional and technical approaches have been developed to track our costs and budgets for implementation. Decades ago and today we record our expenses in a register to calculate the profit or savings. Not only that, many desktop and mobile apps are designed for this purpose. Quicken and Microsoft Money were the first desktop applications built decades ago, but are not known to consumers. We can also predict future costs.

IV. METHODOLOGY

To reduce manual statistics, we recommend a website. This website allows users to keep a digital digital diary. Each user will be required to register on the system at the time of registration, the user will be given an id, which will be used to keep a separate user record. The Budget Tracker program will track user revenue daily. This application takes the user's revenue and divides it into allowed daily expenses. If you skip those day expenses you will be reduced if you earn money then give new expenses for the day the allowable amount, and if you spend less days you will add to the savings. The budget tracking system will produce a report at the end of the month to reflect Revenue through multiple graphs. It will allow you to add to the amount of savings you have saved for specific Celebrations or days such as Birthdays or Birthday Celebrations.

A. ADVANTAGES OF TECHNOLOGY:

- HTML
- CSS
- JAVASCRIPT
- I DO

B. BACK TECHNOLOGY:

- PHP
- MySql

V. PROCESS MODEL USED

The waterfall model is a sequential approach, where each fundamental activity of a process represented as a separate phase, arranged in linear order. In the waterfall model, you must plan and schedule all of the activities before starting working on them (plan- driven process). Waterfall model is used for the project because all the requirements are clear as this project is not dealing with the clients and hence beforehandplanning can be made about how to carry out each phase of development.

VI. WORKING MODEL

Fig. 1: Working Model

Fig. 2: Working Model

VII. CONCLUSION

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A budget helps you to see where your money is going, makes it easier to identify problem areas, helps you to move around where needed and helps you achieve your financial goals. As a business owner or a working person, the better you understand your budget, the more likely you are to stay on top of your financial health. The elements considered in this project are - Source of Income, Focused Costs, Business Cost, Investment, Savings etc. While building this sophisticated cost tracking app, students learn many advanced React & JavaScript themes. Some of them are React Regional Management, Context API, Local Storage, Material UI, and how to create a scalable React folder. But most importantly, the implementation of adding voice power to your applications.

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